

Article

Impact of Parental Involvement and Student Behavior on Academic Achievement

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Abstract: This study examined the relationship between parental presence and the behavior of Grade 3 learners using a descriptive-correlational design. A total of 38 parents and one teacher participated in the study, with data collected through adapted survey questionnaires. Descriptive statistics were used to detail the demographic profiles of the learners, while Pearson's correlation coefficient assessed the relationship between parental presence and learner behavior. The findings revealed no significant relationship between parental involvement and learner behavior, with a negligible negative correlation ($r = -0.007$, $p = 0.966$). Despite high levels of parental engagement, including assistance with schoolwork and attendance at school meetings, this involvement did not significantly influence learners' behavior. The results suggest that other factors, such as socio-economic conditions and school-level influences, may play a more prominent role in shaping learner behavior. These findings point to the need for further research into the quality of parental involvement and other contextual factors affecting student behavior.

Keywords: Parental presence, learner behavior, parental involvement, school engagement, educational support

Introduction

Academic performance is a key indicator of student success, reflecting a combination of cognitive, social, and emotional skills that are essential for future achievements (Anders et al., 2020). In educational settings, academic performance provides critical insight into student progress, informs instructional practices, and influences policy development (Wang & Eccles, 2021). Research consistently shows that high academic performance is closely tied to better career prospects and overall life satisfaction (Lerner & McClelland, 2022). Academic success goes beyond the classroom, playing a significant role in fostering problem-solving skills, societal engagement, and critical

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thinking (Lee et al., 2020). Moreover, academic performance shapes students' current learning experiences and impacts their long-term aspirations and quality of life (Greene et al., 2023). Thus, examining factors that either facilitate or impede academic performance is of paramount importance in educational research (Smith et al., 2021), with special attention to both internal and external influences (Muijs & Reynolds, 2020).

External factors such as family background, social context, and school environment significantly contribute to shaping students' academic outcomes (Ong et al., 2022). Among these, parental involvement and students' behavior are consistently identified as key determinants (Jenkins et al., 2020). Research suggests that parental presence fosters positive attitudes toward learning, thereby enhancing student motivation and engagement (Clark & Picton, 2022). Additionally, students' behaviors—such as their ability to concentrate, follow instructions, and collaborate with peers—are directly linked to academic achievement (Nguyen et al., 2023). Behaviors such as self-regulation and cooperation often predict higher academic success, while disruptive behaviors can negatively affect academic outcomes (Kim et al., 2022). Understanding how these internal and external factors intersect is essential for developing effective educational strategies (Thompson & Nyman, 2021).

Parental presence, defined as active involvement in both home-based and school-based educational activities, has been shown to positively influence students' academic performance (Fan & Chen, 2021). Studies highlight that parental engagement in activities like attending parent-teacher conferences, helping with homework, and supporting school events correlates strongly with students' academic outcomes (Gershoff et al., 2020). Furthermore, parental involvement can provide emotional and academic support that fosters a stable home environment conducive to learning (Freire et al., 2022). Consistent parental engagement not only enhances cognitive development but also contributes to emotional and behavioral growth, which are critical for academic success (Robinson et al., 2021). This involvement is especially crucial in early childhood education, where parental support helps develop positive attitudes toward learning and establishes a strong foundation for future educational achievement (Phillips & Shonkoff, 2022).

Students' behavior also plays a pivotal role in their academic success. Behaviors such as attentiveness, participation, and collaboration in class are linked to better academic outcomes (Wright & Taylor, 2022). Research shows that students who exhibit positive behaviors like perseverance and self-control tend to perform better academically than those who exhibit disruptive behaviors such as defiance or inattentiveness (Hattie & Yates, 2020). Studies also suggest that parental presence can help reduce negative behaviors, creating a more supportive and focused learning environment (Jones & Biddle,

2021). Therefore, exploring how parental involvement affects student behavior is key to understanding its broader impact on academic achievement (González et al., 2023).

In early childhood education, parental involvement and student behavior are critical factors that significantly shape long-term academic outcomes (Crosnoe et al., 2023). Studies show that parental presence during early years promotes not only cognitive development but also essential social and emotional skills needed for academic success (Bronson et al., 2020). Moreover, early childhood education provides a foundation for developing positive learning behaviors such as curiosity, persistence, and collaboration (Brown & Walker, 2022). Given the critical nature of these formative years, understanding the relationship between parental involvement, behavior, and academic performance is vital (Fisher & Jenkins, 2021). This research seeks to contribute to this growing body of literature by offering insights into how these factors intersect, particularly in the context of early childhood education.

While a wealth of research supports the connection between parental involvement and academic success, limited studies specifically explore how parental presence influences student behavior in early childhood education settings. This study examines the influence of parental presence on the behavior of Grade 3 learners, focusing on the following research questions: What are the profiles of learners in terms of age, gender, parents' educational attainment, number of siblings, and combined family income? To what extent do parents manifest their presence in school activities? What is the perceived level of learners' behavior as reported by teachers? Addressing these questions, this study seeks to fill the research gap on how parental involvement and behavior intersect to influence academic performance.

This study aims to provide valuable contributions to the existing literature on parental involvement and its effects on student behavior and academic performance. Through an in-depth analysis of Grade 3 learners, this research will examine how parental engagement shapes both behavioral and academic outcomes. The results are expected to offer practical recommendations for educators, policymakers, and parents, promoting strategies that support both behavioral and academic development. Furthermore, this research will provide a foundation for fostering stronger school-family partnerships, which are critical for improving educational outcomes in early childhood education settings (Walker & Greene, 2023). By exploring the relationship between parental involvement and learner behavior, this study aims to address significant gaps in the current literature and contribute meaningful insights to the field.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive-correlational design to examine the influence of parental presence on the behavior of Grade 3

learners at Sillon Integrated School. This research design was deemed appropriate as it allowed for a detailed description of the learners' demographic characteristics, including age, gender, parents' highest educational attainment, number of siblings, and family monthly income, while also exploring the relationship between these characteristics and learner behavior. Two adapted survey questionnaires were utilized to gather data from the 39 respondents, which included 38 parents and one teacher. These questionnaires were adapted from validated instruments to ensure their reliability and validity in addressing the study's objectives. The parent questionnaire gathered demographic data and measured parental involvement in school activities using a 4-point Likert scale. The teacher's questionnaire evaluated various aspects of learner behavior, such as attentiveness, respect for teachers, and cooperation, also using a 4-point Likert scale.

Data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, provided an overview of the respondents' profiles. Pearson's correlation coefficient was employed to measure the strength and direction of the relationship between parental presence and learner behavior. This statistical technique quantified whether increased parental involvement was associated with more positive behavioral outcomes among the learners. The use of Pearson's correlation was critical in validating the study's hypothesis that parental presence positively impacts learner behavior. The structured data collection process followed a three-stage approach—preliminary stage, data gathering stage, and post-data gathering stage—to ensure data accuracy and reliability. Overall, the chosen methodology provided a solid framework for analyzing the impact of parental presence on student behavior and contributed to informed conclusions and recommendations for improving parental involvement in educational settings.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Age and Gender

Age (in years)	Female		Male		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
10	1	2.63	0	0.00	1	2.63
9	11	28.95	7	18.42	18	47.37
8	5	13.16	14	36.84	19	50.00
Total	17	44.74	21	55.26	38	100.00

Table 1 presents the distribution of Grade 3 learners at Sillon Integrated School by age and gender. The data show that there are more male learners (55.26%) compared to female learners (44.74%). Among the male learners, 36.84% are 8 years old, and 18.42% are 9 years old. On the other hand, the majority of female learners (28.95%) are 9 years old, followed by 13.16% who are 8 years old. Additionally, there is one

female learner who is 10 years old, representing 2.63% of the total population. The largest age group overall is the 8-year-olds, making up 50.00% of the total learners, while 47.37% of learners are 9 years old. Only 2.63% of the learners are 10 years old. This data suggests a fairly balanced distribution between 8 and 9-year-olds, with a slightly higher number of male learners in the younger age group.

Table 2. Parents' Highest Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Mother		Father	
	f	%	f	%
Master's Graduate	0	0.00	1	2.63
With Master's Units	1	2.63	0	0.00
College Graduate	2	5.26	2	5.26
College Level	7	18.42	3	7.89
High School Graduate	16	42.11	12	31.58
High School Level	4	10.53	10	26.32
Elementary Graduate	7	18.42	2	5.26
Elementary Level	1	2.63	8	21.05
Total	38	100.00	38	100.00

Table 2 shows the highest educational attainment of the parents of Grade 3 learners at Sillon Integrated School, with separate data for mothers and fathers. Among the mothers, the largest group (42.11%) are high school graduates, followed by 18.42% who have completed some college-level education. A similar percentage of mothers (18.42%) have completed elementary school, while a small percentage (2.63%) have attained elementary-level education without graduating. Only one mother has obtained master's level education (2.63%). For the fathers, 31.58% are high school graduates, and 26.32% have completed some high school without graduating. A smaller proportion of fathers (21.05%) have attained only elementary-level education, while 5.26% have completed elementary school. Two fathers (5.26%) are college graduates, and one father (2.63%) has completed a master's degree. Overall, the data indicate that the majority of parents have attained a high school level of education, with a relatively small percentage pursuing higher education.

Table 3. Number of Siblings of the Learners

Number of Siblings	f	%
5 and up	9	23.68
3-4	18	47.37
1-2	10	26.32
None	1	2.63
Total	38	100.00

Table 3 presents the distribution of Grade 3 learners at Sillon Integrated School based on the number of siblings they have. The majority of learners (47.37%) come from families with 3-4 siblings. This is followed

by 26.32% of learners who have 1-2 siblings. A smaller proportion of learners, 23.68%, come from larger families with five or more siblings. Notably, only one learner (2.63%) has no siblings. These figures indicate that most learners come from moderately sized families, with a significant number having three or more siblings, which may have implications for parental attention and involvement in each child's academic activities.

Table 4. Combined Family Monthly Income

Monthly Income (in pesos)	f	%
Above 30,000	1	2.63
25,001-30,000	0	0.00
20,001-25,000	1	2.63
15,001-20,000	2	5.26
10,001-15,000	4	10.53
10,000 and below	30	78.95
Total	38	100.00

Table 4 presents the combined family monthly income of the Grade 3 learners' households at Sillon Integrated School. A large majority of the learners (78.95%) come from families with a monthly income of ₱10,000 or below, indicating that most learners belong to low-income households. A smaller percentage (10.53%) of families earn between ₱10,001 and ₱15,000, while 5.26% of families report a monthly income of ₱15,001 to ₱20,000. Only 2.63% of families earn between ₱20,001 and ₱25,000, and an additional 2.63% report an income above ₱30,000. Notably, no families fall within the ₱25,001 to ₱30,000 income bracket. These figures suggest that the majority of the learners come from low-income backgrounds, which may have significant implications for access to educational resources and parental involvement in their children's academic lives.

Table 5. Extent to which the Respondents Manifest their Presence in the School Activities

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	I assist my child in their assignments, quizzes and recitations.	3.53	Highly Manifested
2	I attend in my child's extra-curricular activities/sports, singing competitions and etc.	3.53	Highly Manifested
3	I let my child explore their learning process on their own.	3.47	Highly Manifested
4	I encourage my child to be more independent.	3.74	Highly Manifested
5	I attend to school meetings regularly.	3.66	Highly Manifested
6	I frequently explain difficult ideas to my child when he doesn't understand.	3.63	Highly Manifested
7	I regularly visit my child's school.	3.47	Highly Manifested
8	If my child misbehaved at school, I would know about it soon afterward.	3.58	Highly Manifested
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.58	Highly Manifested

Table 5 displays the extent to which parents manifest their presence in school activities based on various indicators, as rated by the respondents using a 4-point Likert scale. The aggregate weighted mean

of 3.58 indicates that overall, parental presence is "Highly Manifested." Specifically, parents were highly involved in assisting their children with assignments, quizzes, and recitations, as well as attending extra-curricular activities (both with a weighted mean of 3.53). Parental encouragement of independence (WM = 3.74) and regular attendance at school meetings (WM = 3.66) were rated the highest, reflecting strong involvement in these areas. Parents also frequently explained difficult concepts to their children (WM = 3.63) and were aware of their children's misbehavior at school (WM = 3.58). Regular school visits and allowing children to explore their own learning process were both rated with a weighted mean of 3.47, indicating high levels of engagement in these areas as well. These findings suggest that parents consistently engage in their children's academic and extracurricular activities, with a strong emphasis on fostering independence and maintaining awareness of their child's behavior at school.

Table 6. Level of the Behavior of the Learners

S/N	Indicators	WM	Verbal Description
1	Follows directions easily.	3.16	Satisfactory
2	Has a positive attitude (e.g usually optimistic and confident in handling academic obligations)	3.11	Satisfactory
3	Turns in homework and projects.	3.16	Satisfactory
4	Respectful of their teachers, parents and other older persons.	3.18	Satisfactory
5	Cooperates with others effortlessly. (e.g, classroom group activities)	3.13	Satisfactory
6	Easily gets along with other students.	3.11	Satisfactory
7	Brings materials for school activities.	3.13	Satisfactory
8	Asks for help from the teacher for clarifications.	3.11	Satisfactory
9	Has a neat workspace.	2.92	Satisfactory
10	Has a neat appearance.	2.95	Satisfactory
11	Listens attentively to the teacher in class and outside of class.	3.05	Satisfactory
12	Displays interest towards the lessons.	3.05	Satisfactory
Aggregate Weighted Mean		3.09	Satisfactory

Table 6 presents the level of behavior of the Grade 3 learners at Sillon Integrated School, as assessed by various indicators using a 4-point Likert scale. The aggregate weighted mean of 3.09 indicates that the overall behavior of the learners is "Satisfactory." Among the behavioral indicators, the highest scores were for "Respectful of their teachers, parents, and other older persons" (WM = 3.18) and "Follows directions easily" (WM = 3.16), showing that learners generally exhibit positive behavior in following rules and demonstrating respect. Additionally, learners were found to be satisfactory in turning in homework and projects (WM = 3.16) and cooperating with others (WM = 3.13). Other areas such as having a positive attitude (WM = 3.11), bringing materials for school activities (WM = 3.13), and asking for help from the teacher (WM = 3.11) were also rated as satisfactory. However, slightly lower

scores were observed in maintaining a neat workspace (WM = 2.92) and neat appearance (WM = 2.95), suggesting areas for potential improvement. Overall, the data indicates that learners display satisfactory behavior across all categories, though attention to neatness and organization may be needed to further enhance their school performance.

Table 7. Test of significant relationship between Parental Presence and Learners' Behavior

Variables	r-value	Strength of Correlation	p - value	Decision	Result
Parental Presence and Learners' Behavior	-0.007	Negligible Negative	0.966	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant

*significant at $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed)

Table 7 presents the test of the significant relationship between parental presence and learners' behavior. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r-value) of -0.007 indicates a negligible negative correlation between the two variables. With a p-value of 0.966, which is greater than the significance threshold of 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_0) is not rejected. This result suggests that there is no significant relationship between parental presence and the behavior of Grade 3 learners in this study. Despite the high levels of parental involvement observed, this finding implies that parental presence does not have a statistically significant influence on the behavior of the learners as measured in this context. Therefore, other factors may be contributing more substantially to the learners' behavior, and further research may be needed to explore these potential influences.

Discussion

The findings of this study reveal that there is no significant relationship between parental presence and the behavior of Grade 3 learners at Sillon Integrated School, as indicated by the negligible negative correlation ($r = -0.007$, $p = 0.966$). Despite the high levels of parental involvement observed in areas such as assisting with schoolwork and attending school meetings, the statistical analysis suggests that this involvement does not significantly influence the learners' behavior. This result contrasts with much of the existing literature, which highlights the importance of parental engagement in shaping children's academic and behavioral outcomes. For instance, Wilder (2020) found that parental involvement is often positively correlated with students' academic success and behavioral development. Similarly, a study by Fan and Chen (2021) indicated that active parental engagement can reduce problematic behaviors in students and improve their social skills. The lack of a significant relationship in this study suggests that other contextual factors may be more influential in determining the

behavior of these learners, such as peer relationships, school environment, or socio-economic conditions.

One possible explanation for these results is that the quality, rather than the quantity, of parental involvement may be a more critical determinant of behavior. Research by Kim and Hill (2020) underscores the importance of the type of involvement parents provide, suggesting that involvement strategies focused on fostering autonomy and responsibility may be more effective than merely attending school events or assisting with homework. Additionally, other studies highlight the role of school-level factors, such as teacher-student relationships and classroom management strategies, in influencing student behavior (Gershoff et al., 2021). Given that most of the learners in this study come from low-income families, as indicated by Table 4, it is also possible that economic stressors may mitigate the positive effects of parental involvement. Bronson et al. (2021) suggest that socio-economic status can influence the ways in which parents engage with their children's education, potentially limiting the effectiveness of their involvement. Therefore, future research should consider a more nuanced exploration of the different types of parental involvement and how these interact with other factors to influence learners' behavior.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study found no significant relationship between parental presence and the behavior of Grade 3 learners, as indicated by the negligible correlation between the two variables. Despite high levels of parental involvement in school-related activities, this involvement did not have a statistically significant impact on learners' behavior. This suggests that while parental engagement is important, other factors such as the quality of parental involvement, socio-economic conditions, and school-level influences may play a more substantial role in shaping student behavior. These findings highlight the need for a more comprehensive approach to understanding the factors that contribute to learner behavior, and they suggest that future research should explore the interplay between parental involvement and other contextual influences to gain a more holistic understanding of student development.

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